

Termination Plan for Swedish National Data Service (SND)

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Swedish National Data Service

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Description of SND's activities

According to the Swedish Research Council's (VR) specific terms and conditions for infrastructure grants to SND (VR reference number 2021–00165_9), the University of Gothenburg (administrating organization), Chalmers University of Technology, Karolinska Institutet, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Lund University, Stockholm University, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Umeå University, and Uppsala University are tasked with managing and developing SND. The purpose is specified in the specific terms and conditions (in italics below).¹

The purpose of the infrastructure is:

- 1. To facilitate the sharing of research data in a simple, secure, and reliable manner, simultaneously meeting the requirements for preservation, access, and sharing.*
- 2. To make data visible and provide user statistics by displaying research data nationally and internationally and provide information on how data are shared and cited.*
- 3. To facilitate reliable access to searchable, high-quality, and well-documented research data, along with information on how these data can be accessed and reused.*

The approved funding period extends from 2023 to 2026, with funding from the Swedish Research Council and the SND consortium.

SND's operations include close collaboration with a network comprising 28 higher education institutions and research organizations (in May 2022) that are establishing local units for managing research data with the aim of making research data findable and accessible for reuse in future research, following the principles of open science.

Background and directives for the termination plan

As per the agreement with VR, it is the responsibility of the administrating organization to establish a termination plan according to section 2.2. of the special terms and conditions (in italics below):

The Administrating Organization is also responsible for:

[...]

- ensuring a termination plan exists. The termination plan should describe how the infrastructure will manage a situation when the Swedish Research Council's support is discontinued. The plan should address how previously made investments, collected samples, and data will be utilised in a structured and purposeful manner.*

Furthermore, there is a general condition concerning early discontinuation of the payment of funding in section 4.3 of VR's specific conditions and in section 5 of the general terms and conditions.

¹ The citations from terms and conditions from and agreements with VR are translations and for reference only.

In the consortium agreement, the termination plan is addressed in section 10, where it is broadly regulated that (in italics below):

After consultation with VR, the Administrating Organization may decide on early termination of SND's activities and this Agreement in accordance with the established termination plan. The responsibility for termination costs is distributed among the Parties in accordance with the termination plan, or otherwise as is reasonable, primarily considering the support provided to each Party.

Furthermore, the consortium agreement regulates how funds and collaborative results will be managed in the event of termination.

Decision on termination

The agreement for funding from VR expires on 31 December 2028. If the agreement is not extended or if the support is terminated prematurely, termination should occur according to this termination plan.

Costs and consequences

Termination entails significant costs. An estimation of costs must be made when it becomes relevant. A consequence analysis should also be included.

Termination, sub-processes

The termination of activities within or after the project period can be divided into the sub-processes below.

Transfer to other activities

An assessment is conducted to determine which of SND's activities can continue with alternative funding and which must be terminated. A specific investigation shall be conducted regarding whether data and associated metadata deposited to the SND CARE service can be made accessible and stored with another organization. Special consideration must be given to SND's responsibility as a consortium representative in the DOI Foundation.

Financial review

Documentation is compiled for the calculation of termination costs for personnel, data, equipment, and other resources. Based on this information, an agreement is reached with VR regarding the size of support during Year 1 and Year 2 from the date of the termination decision. The balance of disbursed funds versus co-financing from consortium members is considered so that the co-financing equals the agreed-upon share as per the VR agreement.

Reassignment or termination of staff

Regular processes for reassignment or termination are initiated.

Compilation and transfer of knowledge and expertise

An investigation is conducted into how the knowledge and expertise accumulated within the activities can be compiled and transferred.

Hardware

Equipment or other hardware purchased within the activities, according to the asset register or equivalent, is transferred to other activities at GU (University of Gothenburg) or scrapped.

Internal systems

The internal systems developed and managed at SND are terminated or transferred, documented, and archived according to a specific termination plan for the system.

Information

Research organizations, authorities, and other users of SND's services are informed well in advance that the services will be terminated or transferred to another organization.

National and international agreements and commitments

SND's memberships, mandates, agreements, and commitments in national and international organizations and projects are transferred, if possible, to another organization or terminated and concluded.

Archiving

An investigation is conducted to determine the relevant information to be archived and where and how it should be done.

Documentation

Termination is documented to facilitate reconstruction.

Termination schedule

Action plan year 1

- An assessment of activities and outcomes at SND is conducted and, in consultation with VR, decisions are made regarding what can continue under different management and what needs complete termination.
- Reassignment or termination of staff is initiated.
- Termination of operations is initiated.
- Existing contracts are terminated.
- Information is provided to those who have deposited data and associated metadata with the SND CARE service, can remain accessible/stored. Special consideration is given to data from a research principal who is no longer active.
- Information to researchers who have deposited data with SND CARE is initiated.
- A review of SND's responsibility as a consortium member of DataCite is made, leading to a decision of how the consortium can continue.
- Information is provided to users of SND's services and other stakeholders.

Year 1 objectives

- Decisions about what can be transferred to other operations have been made.
- Termination of staff has been initiated.
- Termination of operations has been initiated.
- Existing contracts have been terminated.
- The review of how data and metadata can remain accessible and stored is concluded.
- Decisions about whether data shall be returned to their research principals have been made.
- Decisions about how to manage data from a research principal who is no longer active have been made.
- Necessary information has been conveyed to those who have deposited data with SND CARE.
- A decision about a continued operation of the consortium in DataCite has been made and responsibility transferred to another party.
- Necessary information has been conveyed to users of SND's services and other stakeholders.

Action plan year 2

- Configuration of technical systems is finalized.
- Transfer of activities to other operations is carried out as agreed upon.

- Hardware is transferred to other operations or scrapped.
- Internal systems are terminated, documented, and archived.
- Relevant information from the activities is archived.
- A support function is maintained during the year to receive and assist users and others who need redirection to other services.
- SND's websites are shut down.
- Transfer of data and associated metadata is carried out as agreed upon.
- DOIs linking to landing pages in SND's resources are redirected.
- Any reconciliation of surplus/deficit of the finances is completed.

Year 2 objectives

- Configuration of technical systems is completed.
- Transfer of activities is completed.
- Hardware is transferred to other operations or scrapped.
- Internal systems are terminated, documented, and archived.
- Relevant information from activities is transferred to the university archive for archiving.
- SND's websites are closed.
- All DOIs linking to landing pages in SND's resources are redirected.
- Any reconciliation of surplus/deficit of the finances is completed.